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CONSTANT FREQUENCY HYSTERETIC CONTROLLER FOR THREE LEVEL BUCK CONVERTER

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Abstract

Dynamic response is the output overshoot or undershoot that occurs when converter output load or supply voltage is suddenly varied. Dynamic response is very important in applications where converter supplying power to the load, due to the large and sudden changes in load. Three Level Buck converter topology that is preferred for point of load applications such as laptops, cellular phones, microprocessors etc. This paper presents a constant frequency hysteretic PWM controller for three level buck converter for improving dynamic response. In order to verify the effectiveness of the controller a simulation model and hardware prototype are developed. The output voltage recovery time, output voltage undershoot and overshoot during load step change and input voltage step change are verified. Simulation and experimental results show a significant improvement in the dynamic response of the three level buck converter with constant frequency hysteretic PWM controller. The hysteretic controller takes advantages of both faster dynamic response performance and simpler control structure.

Keywords – dynamic response, hysteretic controller, three level buck converter, PSIM

I. Introduction

Power electronics circuits convert electric power from one form to other using electronic devices. Power electronics circuits function by using semiconductor devices as switches, thereby controlling or modifying a voltage or current. The objective of a power electronics circuit is to match the voltage and current requirements of the load to those of the source. Power electronics circuits convert one type or level of a voltage or current waveform to another and are hence called converters. Converters serve as an interface between the source and load. Power electronic converters are used to control and condition the flow of electrical energy between two systems. The insertion of a power electronic converter between the two systems becomes essential to achieve compatibility between them and to achieve important performance objectives.

DC-DC Converters are widely used in regulated switched mode dc power supplies. Switch mode dc to dc converters are used to convert the unregulated dc input into a controlled dc output at a desired voltage level. The main requirements of a dc dc converter are steady state requirement and transient state requirements. Steady-state requirement is the load voltage regulation. In most of the cases, the load requires a well-regulated voltage of desired magnitude. Besides, the switching ripple in

the load voltage is desired to be kept low. Among the several transient-state load requirements, permissible overshoots and dips in the converter states (inductor current, output voltage), time taken by the load voltage to recover after a sudden disturbance, and hold-up time after a failure in the supply voltage are of prime importance.

In [1] hysteretic controller is used to improve the dynamic response of three level buck converter. In [2] three-level buck converter is modified by adding an extra switch, diode and capacitor. Capacitor current fed forward control technique is used to detect the transients. In [3] controller consist of comparator with hysteresis and an amplifier. In [4] hysteretic PWM control scheme uses hysteretic comparator and feedback resistors. In [5] hysteretic PWM controller consists of hysteretic comparator and an RC network is connected in parallel with the inductor, the ramp voltage for the comparator is provided from the RC network. In [6] combined linear non-linear controller is discussed. In [7] different topologies of three level DC-DC converters and feed forward control scheme for DC-DC converters are discussed. In [8] three level buck converter is used for envelope tracking in radio frequency applications. In [9] a current control method is suggested for flying capacitor voltage balance. In [10] hysteretic controller is implemented using passive filter network and hysteretic comparator. In [11] output capacitor current defines the hysteresis band. In [12] hysteretic current control and hysteretic voltage control are discussed.

II. Three Level Buck Converter

Multilevel topologies have several advantages to offer over two-level topologies in high voltage applications. Multi-level converter topologies are of two types diode clamped and capacitive clamped. In these topologies clamping diodes or flying capacitor is used to ensure the voltage balance between series connected semiconductor switches.

Fig. 1 shows the circuit diagram of three level buck converter. V_A labels the voltage of node A with respect to the ground. In this topology, the converter can operate at three voltage levels ($0, 0.5V_{in}, V_{in}$).

Fig 1. Three Level Buck Converter

When both the switches are conducting voltage at node A will be V_{in} , when one switch and one diode is conducting voltage will be $0.5V_{in}$, when both diodes are conducting voltage will be 0. Because of the additional voltage level, the size of the inductor used in design of the converter is small for the same output current ripple. The flying capacitor voltage is maintained at half the input source voltage. One way of doing this is by driving switches S_1 and S_2 180° out of phase to each other.

The three level buck converter can greatly reduce magnetic size or reduce the switching frequency without suffering a bulky magnetic component. The voltage across the inductor the inductor ripple current for the three level converter for duty ratio <0.5 is given by:

$$\Delta i_{Lpk-pk} = \frac{V_{in} \cdot (0.5 - D) \cdot D}{L \cdot f_s} \tag{1}$$

The value of inductance is give by:

$$L = \left(1 - \frac{2V_o}{V_{in}}\right) \frac{RT}{2} \tag{2}$$

Where V_{in} is the input voltage, D is the duty cycle, L is the filter inductance, and f_s is the switching frequency.

The peak to peak capacitor voltage ripple is given by:

$$\Delta V_{L,pk-pk} = \frac{D \cdot I_o}{C_f \cdot f_s} \tag{3}$$

Where D is the duty cycle, I_o is the output current, C_f is the flying capacitance value, and f_s is the switching frequency. To maintain a small voltage ripple, a large enough flying capacitance must be selected based on the design requirements. For higher duty cycles, output currents and lower frequencies the amount of capacitance required increases.

The inductor current slew rates for load step-up and load step-down changes can be expressed as

$$\frac{di_L}{dt} = \frac{V_A - V_O}{L_{chreabuck}} = \frac{0.5V_{in} - V_O}{L_{chreabuck}} \tag{4}$$

$$\frac{di_L}{dt} = \frac{V_A - V_O}{L_{chreabuck}} = \frac{-V_O}{L_{chreabuck}} \tag{5}$$

The value of inductor in three level buck converter is less so the inductor current slew rate increases so the dynamic response of the three level buck converter increases. Dynamic response can further be improved by adopting a suitable control strategy.

III. Control Technique

The control technique employed to improve the dynamic response is constant frequency hysteretic control technique. The control circuit consists of a hysteretic comparator and error amplifier. Fig. 2 shows a presented hysteretic PWM controller.

Fig 2 Hysteretic PWM controller

The most peculiar part of the controller is hysteretic comparator part. The triangular voltage V_N is connected to the comparator negative input and the ground. The voltage of positive input of the comparator V_P is obtained from output voltage of error amplifier and V_I is the output voltage of the comparator. The switching frequency of presented controller is basically determined by the frequency of the triangular waveform and the hysteretic window voltage. Type II compensator is used in order to reduce the output voltage ripple.

Upper and lower threshold voltage V_H and V_L are determined by the output voltage of error amplifier V_A , comparator high level output voltage V_{OH} , low level output voltage V_{OL} , and resistors R_a , R_b as follows expression

$$V_H = \frac{R_a}{R_a + R_b} * V_A + \frac{R_b}{R_a + R_b} * V_{OH} \tag{6}$$

$$V_L = \frac{R_a}{R_a + R_b} * V_A + \frac{R_b}{R_a + R_b} * V_{OL} \tag{7}$$

The comparator with built-in hysteresis is sometimes known as a “Schmitt trigger”. The Hysteresis voltage is defined as the difference in these thresholds.

$$V_{HYS} = V_H - V_L \tag{8}$$

Hysteresis voltage V_{HYS} should be kept greater than the peak-peak value of the noise signal.

IV. Simulation Results

In order to verify the performance of the converter with hysteretic PWM controller a simulation model has been developed using PSIM. Converter is designed for an input voltage of 50V, output voltage 19.5V, duty ratio 0.39 and switching frequency 10kHz.

Fig 3 shows the waveform of hysteretic controller. V_p is the voltage on the positive input of the hysteretic comparator, V_n is the negative input of the hysteretic comparator. The upper threshold voltage is 3V and lower threshold voltage is 2.5. The output of the comparator is given to D-FlipFlop and AND gates to generate switching pattern of the converter.

Fig 3 Waveform of Hysteretic PWM Controller

Fig 4 shows the output voltage during step change in load. (a) shows the output voltage during decrease in load. Output voltage undershoot is 1.26 V and recovery time is 0.033 s. (b) shows the output voltage during increase in load. Output voltage overshoot is 1.03 V and output voltage recovery time is 0.052 s.

Fig 4 Output voltage during step change in load

Fig 5 shows the output voltage during step change in input voltage . (a)shows the output voltage during step decrease in input voltage. Output voltage undershoot is 0.3 V and recovery time is 0.016 s. (b) shows the output voltage during step increase in input voltage. Output voltage overshoot is 0.2 V and output voltage recovery time is 0.023 s.

Fig 5 Output voltage during step change in input voltage

V. Experimental Results

In order to verify the performance of the three buck converter with the proposed hysteretic PWM controller, a hardware prototype has been developed. Table I and Table II shows the parameters for the hardware implementation of three level buck converter.

Table I

Parameters	Symbol	Value	Unit
Input Voltage	V_{in}	40-50	V
Output Voltage	V_{out}	19.5	V
Inductor	L	900	μ H
Output Filtering Capacitor	C_o	6600	μ F
Flying Capacitor	C_f	100	μ F
Frequency	f_s	10000	Hz
Resistor	R	11-41	Ω

Table II

Parameters	Value	Unit
R_i	10	k Ω
R_f	1000	k Ω
R_a	100	k Ω
R_b	100	k Ω
C_f	0.01	μ F
R_1	100	k Ω
C_1	0.1	μ F
C	0.1	μ F

Fig 6 shows the experimental setup of the three level buck converter with hysteretic controller. Table III shows the components used for the experimental verification.

Fig 6

Table III

MOSFET Switches	IRFP250
Diodes	U1560
Op-Amps	TL084
D flipflop	74LS74
AND gate	74LS08
Gate driver IC	TLP250

(i) Waveforms of Hysteretic Controller

Fig 7 (a) shows the inverting input of the hysteretic comparator and fig 7 (b) shows the non inverting input of the hysteretic comparator or the hysteretic band.

Fig 7

Fig 8(a) shows the output of the hysteretic and fig 8(b) shows the switching pulses to the switches S_1 and S_2

Fig 8

(ii) Step Change in Load

Fig 9 shows the output voltage during step change in the load. Fig 9(a) shows the shows the output voltage during step decrease in load. Initially the load is 41Ω, the corresponding output voltage is 19.4V. Then the load is varied from 41 Ω to 11Ω the output voltage becomes 19.2 V. Output voltage undershoot is 0.5V, change in voltage ΔV during step change in load is 160mV and recovery time is 62 ms.

Fig 9

Fig 9(b) shows the shows the output voltage during step increase in load Initially the load is 11 Ω, the corresponding output voltage is 19 V. Then the load is varied from 11Ω to 41Ω output voltage become 19.5 V. Output voltage overshoot is 1V, change in voltage ΔV during step change in load is 480mV and output voltage recovery time is 80 ms.

(iii) Step Change in Input Voltage

Fig 10 shows the output voltage during step change in the input . Fig 10(a) shows the output and input voltage during step decrease in input voltage. Here the input voltage is varied from 50 V to 40 V. Initially the input voltage is 50 V, the output voltage is 19.4 V then the input voltage is decreased to 40 V the output voltage remains the same. Output voltage undershoot is 0.2 V, change in voltage during step change in input voltage is zero V and recovery time is 150 ms.

Fig 10

Fig 10(b) shows the output voltage during step increase in input voltage. Here the input voltage is varied from 40 to 50V. Initially the input voltage is 40 V, the output voltage is 19.2 V then the input voltage is increased to 50 V the output voltage becomes 19.4V. Output voltage overshoot is 0.8 V, change in voltage during step change in input voltage is 0.2V and output voltage recovery time is 190 ms.

(iv) Comparison of Output Voltage during Step Change in Load

Table IV shows the comparison of output voltage during step change in load. Here the step change in load is 30 Ω. Comparison mainly focus on output voltage undershoot/ overshoot and output voltage recovery time.

TABLE IV

Type of Load Change	Without Controller		With Hysteretic Controller	
	Voltage Undershoot(V)	Recovery time (ms)	Voltage Undershoot(V)	Recovery time (ms)
Decrease in load	1.9	270	0.5	62
Increase in load	Voltage Overshoot(V)	Recovery time (ms)	Voltage Overshoot(V)	Recovery time (ms)
	1.8	200	1	80

(v) Comparison of Output Voltage during Step Change in Input Voltage

Table V shows the comparison of output voltage during step change in input voltage. Here the step change in input voltage is 10 V. Comparison mainly focus on output voltage undershoot/ overshoot and output voltage recovery time.

TABLE V

Type of Input Voltage Change	Without Controller		With Hysteretic Controller	
	Voltage Undershoot(V)	Recovery time (ms)	Voltage Undershoot(V)	Recovery time (ms)
Decrease in input voltage	1.9	200	0.2	150
	Voltage Overshoot(V)	Recovery time (ms)	Voltage Overshoot(V)	Recovery time (ms)
Increase in input voltage	2.7	280	0.8	190

Conclusion

Dynamic response of dc–dc power electronic converters has always been a challenging task. Three-level buck converter is a topology preferred for high-power applications as voltage stress on the switches is smaller than a standard buck converter. In this paper a constant frequency hysteretic PWM control strategy has been used for improving the dynamic response of a three-level buck converter. In order to verify the dynamic response of the three level buck converter with the hysteretic PWM controller first a simulation model has been developed using PSIM later a hardware prototype has been developed. The output voltage recovery time, output voltage undershoot and overshoot during load step change and input voltage step change are verified. Both simulation and experimental results show that by using this approach dynamic response of three level buck converter is improved, good load regulation and line regulation are obtained. The hysteretic controller takes advantages of both faster dynamic response performance and simpler control structure. Dynamic response of the three level buck converter can further be improved by modifying the three level buck converter topology. The control scheme used can be easily expanded to different DC-DC converter topologies.

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